

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MOBILE APPLICATION PERFECT LADY IN MONITORING THE START AND DEVELOPMENT OF MENOPAUSE

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Abstract

The present article is devoted to innovation digital solution project to support women during menopause. The International team of experts create a mobile application to provide the woman a widely accessible modern tool to self-control and self-arrange of menopause changes for prolonging and conservation of economic and social activity.

Keywords: Menopause, digital project, mobile application for health and wellness, women's economic and social activity.

Menopause is a natural biological process that should be considered an important stage in a woman's life cycle. Menopause symptoms affect a woman's personal and professional life. However, women are still told to come to terms with aging and accept the severe symptoms of menopause as a given. Perimenopausal health care plays a key role in promoting healthy aging and improving quality of life.

Practice shows that for a considerable number of women this period is associated with significant mental suffering, lack of support, adequate medical care and even basic knowledge about the characteristics of the period and the possibilities of lifestyle changes. In many countries around the world, the topic of menopause is sacralized and endowed with negative social stereotypes that really affect a woman's success and social activity.

The above reasons indicate the relevance of the topic of early medical education of women around the world about monitoring the onset of menopause and effective socially active ways of living during this period.

Menopause is a significant transition period not only from a biological but also from a social point of view. The number of postmenopausal women is growing every year. According to WHO, in 2021, women aged 50 and over made up 26% of all women and girls in the world, up from 22% a decade earlier. In addition, women, on average, live longer than men. In 2019, women aged 60 worldwide could expect to live an average of 21 more years¹. According to WHO forecasts, by 2030 the population over 60 years of age is expected to double².

This means that as the number of women approaching menopause increases, so does the proportion who experience severe consequences of this period, including social disintegration and loss of economic activity³.

The most recognizable symptoms traditionally associated with menopause include are hot flushes and night sweats; changes in the regularity and flow of the menstrual cycle, culminating in cessation of menstruation; vaginal dryness, pain during sexual intercourse and incontinence; difficulty sleeping/insomnia and changes in mood, depression, and/or anxiety. However, there are special symptoms, which have a high risk to lead the woman to losing her social activity status, job, career and even social contacts. Today we can tell about increase effects of body composition and cardiovascular risk. «Women's advantage over men in terms of cardiovascular disease gradually disappears with the significant decline in estrogen levels after menopause. Menopause can also result in the weakening of the pelvic support structures, increasing the risk of pelvic organ prolapse. Loss of bone density at menopause is a significant contributor to higher rates of osteoporosis and fractures»⁴.

The WHO statistical report highlights perimenopausal women need access to quality health services and communities and systems that can support them. The problem is in that both awareness and access to menopause-related information and services remain a significant challenge in most countries. Menopause is often not discussed within families, communities, workplaces, or health-care settings.

WHO confirms the global lack of training of doctors in the treatment and management of perimenopausal women and the low level of awareness of women themselves about this period of life.

Women more often do not know that symptoms they experience are related to menopause, or that there are counselling and treatment options that can help alleviate discomfort. Those experiencing menopausal symptoms may feel embarrassed or ashamed to draw attention to their experiences and ask for support.

¹ Menopause. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause> Date of link: 14.06.2024.

² Ageing and health. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health> 15.06.2024.

³ World health statistics 2024: monitoring health for the

SDGs, sustainable development goals

URL: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240094703> Date of link: 15.06.2024.

⁴ Menopause. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause> Date of link: 14.06.2024.

According to report of UNISEF, especially this problem is closed for decision by traditional methods in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) and the Arab States region⁵.

In response to the problem of increasing negative scenarios for living menopause around the world, WHO formulates the principle «Public health challenges related to menopause». To decide this problem which is a part of global problem of life quality increasing and sustainable development is necessary to raise awareness of menopause and its impact on women at individual and societal levels, as well as on countries' health and socioeconomic development; advocating for the inclusion of diagnosis, treatment and counselling related to management of menopausal symptoms as part of universal health coverage; promoting the inclusion of training on menopause and treatment options in pre-service curricula for health workers; and emphasizing a life course approach to health and well-being, by ensuring that women have access to appropriate health information and services to promote healthy ageing and a high quality of life before, during and after menopause.

To solve this problem, a team of authors has developed a digital solution within the WHO approach «Public health challenges related to menopause» in the form of the «Perfect Lady» mobile application for maximum coverage of menopause's information.

The international team of Perfect Lady app creators are experts in developing innovative digital solutions to socially significant problems. Anisimov Valentin is a director of solutions in the field of HMI (London, UK), Anisimova Irina is a PhD in Sociology, UX/UI-Designer, expert in development of innovation project in social, medicine, education, author of book «Project-telling: positioning by projects» (London, UK), Ispolinova Anastasia is a doctor in gynecology, an executive director of the clinic «Ultra Safe» (Tbilisi, Georgia), Korniiichuk Iurii clinical embryologist, Head of IVF laboratory medical clinic «Birth» (Batumi, Georgia).

Perfect Lady aims are to support women during this important period, providing them with the knowledge and tools to reassess their health and lifestyle. For this relevant problem awareness and support are key to improving the quality of life for menopausal women.

Project goals:

1. Education and information. Providing health information about perimenopause and menopause. An explanation of the physical and emotional changes that occur during this period.

2. Diagnostics and individual approach. We have developed functionality that will allow women to undergo specialized tests to determine their current hormonal state. The application will help women determine exactly what age period they are in and what health changes are associated with this.

3. Counseling and therapy. The application will provide access to consultations with doctors. We offer

a comprehensive approach that includes medical advice and lifestyle advice.

Implementation methods:

- Mobile app. Development of an interactive application with information materials, tests and the ability to sign up for consultations.

- Educational activities. Organization of webinars and seminars with the participation of leading experts in the field of gynecology and endocrinology, available through the application.

When designing the mobile application interface, the following user scenarios and functions were implemented:

1. User experience «Your Lady type (virtual type)» - training in self-observation, self-diagnosis during menopause.

2. User experience «Timetable» - planning critical activities (sports, nutrition, water, cosmetics advice);

3. Self-diagnosis - statistics of critical indicators in Infographics.

4. Mobile doctor - telemedicine consultation.

5. Webinars - training, solving psychological problems.

6. Notifications - feedback from the doctor, once a month feedback on the dynamics of indicators.

7. Profile - personal medical card.

8. Medical news - the latest advances in medicine on menopause.

To implement the functionality, the application includes:

1. Server part supporting a client database, a video communication server and a neural network responsible for automated self-diagnosis.

2. Client applications implemented on Android and iOS operating systems with functionality divided into a user interface and an interface for doctors. All versions of client applications are used to visualize the logic implemented on the server side.

Project aims to provide women with the knowledge and tools they need to approach menopause with confidence and understanding. We believe that awareness and support are key to improving your quality of life and become a solution in prolonging women's economic and social activity and overcoming gender inequality in the economic and social spheres.

Literature

1. Ageing and health. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health> 15.06.2024.

2. Anisimova I. Project development process in Project-telling methodology/ I. Anisimova - Budapest, Hungary: The scientific heritage No 133 (2024) – p. 58-61. - ISSN 9215 — 0365

3. Menopause. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause> Date of link: 14.06.2024.

4. Menopause. URL: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/menopause> Date of link: 14.06.2024.

⁵ Situational analysis of women and girls in the MENA and Arab states region a decade review 2010-2020. URL: <https://www.unicef.org/mena/media/14311/file/54949%20-%20Design%20MENA%20SitAn%20Report%20-%20v10.pdf> Date of link: 15.06.2024.

%20Design%20MENA%20SitAn%20Report%20-%20v10.pdf Date of link: 15.06.2024.

5. Situational analysis of women and girls in the MENA and Arab states region a decade review 2010-2020. URL: <https://www.unicef.org/mena/media/14311/file/54949%20-%20De-sign%20MENA%20SitAn%20Report%20-%20v10.pdf.pdf> Date of link: 15.06.2024.

6. World health statistics 2024: monitoring health for the SDGs, sustainable development goals. URL: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240094703> Date of link: 15.06.2024.